

Cam Shaft Oil Hole Testing Gadget

Dhawale Mahesh Balkrishna

TY AE Marathwada Mitra Mandal's Polytechnic, Pune/MSBTE Maharashtra India

UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF

Prof. Kurhade A.S.

Department Of Automobile Engineering Marathwada Mitra Mandal's Polytechnic, Pune/MSBTE
Maharashtra India

Abstract

In this project we focus on quality checking of product. From older day the cam shaft checking is done by very simple method, they use one small metal rod. Which is smaller in diameter compared to oil hole diameter of camshaft is inserted in oil hole and another is inserting in hole which are provided on general hole, which is perpendicular to the axis of shaft. When both rod are touch to each other then quality checking person know the hole is incorrect. This project established new way idea of product checking in advance.

Introduction

Quality control consist of all those activity's , which are to design to define , maintain and control specific quality of product within reasonable limits .it is the systematic regulation of all variable affecting goodness of the end product. It does not attempt to achieve the perfect quality but to secure satisfactory or reasonable quality at a competitive level.

Project: -

“CAM SHAFT OIL HOLE
TESTING GADGET”

List of equipment

- Camshaft.
- V-Block
- Proximity Sensor
- Air Pipe
- Air Nozzle.
- Indicating Lamps.

Project Cost

- Project cost up to Rs- 10,000/-.

Working

The main concept of this project is quality checking of camshaft. As per shown in construction diagram. The cam shaft which is to be checked is placed on v-block then sensor is actuated and sends the signal to the valve. Then valve is opened start air is supply.

When air supply starts it passes through the oil hole of a camshaft also passes on general surface of camshaft. When air delivered from oil hole it strike on sheet metal plate. At the same time sensor sense the moment of plate and give signal on board. By this method camshaft can be checked. If the camshaft is not ok that means oil hole are not in correct position.

Advantages

- It takes less time to check the camshaft.
- To improve quality checking
- It avoids rejection.
- Lees maintenance

DISADVANTAGES

- It more costly.

Future Scope

- This equipment is useful for camshaft producing company.
- Use in the automobile company who buy from the camshaft from vender company.

References

- www.historytv18.com
- www.discoveryscience.com
- www.goggle.com